

Peristaltic Transport of Conducting Newtonian Nanofluid with Slip and Heat Transfer in an Inclined Tapered Asymmetric Channel

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Abstract - The peristaltic transport of Newtonian nanofluids with slip, heat transfer and MHD effects in an inclined tapered asymmetric channel is studied under long wavelength and low-Reynolds number assumptions. The flow is examined in a wave frame of reference moving with velocity of the wave. The expressions for temperature, nanoparticle concentration, pressure rise, velocity and stream function are derived analytically. The physical behavior of different parameters on Newtonian nanofluids flow has been presented graphically. It is concluded that pressure rise increases with inclination parameter and Thermophoresis parameter and decreases with Brownian motion parameter. The velocity decreases with non-uniform parameter. The effects of Thermophoresis parameter, Brownian motion parameter, Prandtl number and radiation parameter on temperature and nanoparticles concentration are also discussed. The trapping phenomenon is also discussed at the end of the article.

Keywords- Nanofluids, brownian motion parameter, thermophoresis parameter, tapered asymmetric channel, Reynolds number, peristaltic transport, trapping phenomena.

I. INTRODUCTION

At present, peristaltic transport has received considerable attention in engineering as well as in physiological sciences. The peristaltic motion involves the physiological phenomena, like blood flow through blood vessels, urine transport from kidney to bladder through the ureter, movement of chime in the gastrointestinal tract, the movement of spermatozoa in the ducts afferents of the male reproductive tract and the ovum in the female fallopian tube, the locomotion of some worms, transport of lymph in the lymphatic vessels and vasomotion of small blood vessels such as arterioles, venules and capillaries. Since the first investigation made by Latham [1], several Researchers [2-9] have made attempts to investigate peristaltic motion of different types of fluids through different geometries. In recent years, enormous effort has been given to the study of nanofluids due to its important role in medical science, energetic, biology, biomedical and processing system engineering such as biological organisms on their primary cellular level. Choi [10] was the first who introduced the term nanofluid in his effort to enhance the thermal conductivity of the fluids. Later, Junemo Koo et al. [11] analyzed the nanoparticle motion mechanisms on the thermal conductivity of nanofluids and concluded that the Brownian motion effect on thermal conductivity decreases with particle size, approaching the thermal conductivity value of the conventional case. Analysis of convective instability and heat transfer characteristics of nanofluids was made by Jake Kima et al. [12] and their results shows that a rod-like particle is more effective to enhance the heat transfer characteristics of a nanofluid than a spherical one. Xiang-Qi Wang et al. [13] gave a review on slip effects on mixed convective peristaltic transport of copper-water nanofluid in an inclined channel on nanofluids - part I: theoretical and numerical investigations. Saima Noreen et al. [14] studied the mixed convection flow of Nanofluid in presence of an inclined magnetic field and they used shooting technique in solving governing partial differential equations. Fahad Munir Abbasi [15] examined the

slip effects on mixed convective peristaltic transport of copper-water nanofluid in an inclined channel and revealed that the addition of copper nanoparticles reduces the pressure gradient, axial velocity at the center of channel.

Mehmood et al. [16] investigated the heat transfer on peristaltic flow of fourth grade fluid in inclined asymmetric channel with partial slip and pumping and trapping phenomena are analyzed for increasing slip parameter. Safia Akram [17] examined the effects of nanofluid on peristaltic flow of a carreau fluid model in an inclined magnetic field. kothandapani and prakash[18] gave an application to the cancer therapy with the study of peristaltic transport carreau nanofluid under the effect of magnetic field in a tapered asymmetric channel. Sayed et al. [19] reported the influence of slip and convective boundary conditions on peristaltic transport of non-newtonian nanofluids in an inclined asymmetric channel. Sreenadh et al. [20] gave an analytical solution for peristaltic flow of conducting nanofluid in an asymmetric channel with slip effect of velocity, temperature and concentration with applications in peristaltic pumping through corrugative and non-corrugative pipes.

II. NOMENCLATURE

a_1, a_2 - amplitude of the waves d- half width of the channel m - non uniform parameter λ - wavelength of the peristaltic wave c - wave speed ϕ_0 - phase difference μ - viscosity M - Hartmann number B_0 - uniform magnetic filed P - pressure Rn - radiation parameter ρ - density of the fluid Θ -mean flow in wave frame	Q - mean flow rate in laboratory frame F - time average flow rate ψ - stream function α inclination parameter Gr_t temperature Grashof number Gr_c mass Grashof number Re - Reynolds number Pr - Prandtl number θ - temperature distribution ϕ - nanoparticle concentration Nt - Brownian motion parameter Nb - Thermophoresis parameter L - slip parameter
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Motivated by the above literature, we made an attempt to study the peristaltic transport of Newtonian Nanofluids with slip, heat transfer and MHD effects in an inclined tapered asymmetric channel under long-wavelength and low-Reynolds number assumptions in wave frame analysis. Analytical expressions are derived for pressure rise, velocity, temperature, nanoparticle concentration and stream function.

III. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

We consider the peristaltic flow of a Newtonian MHD nanofluid in a tapered vertical asymmetric channel with slip effect. The flow is generated by the propagation of train of a progressive sinusoidal waves along the walls of the channel with a constant speed c . The deformation of the walls in the cartesian coordinate system (\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) of the fixed frame is given by

$$H_1 = -a_1 \sin \left[\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (\bar{X} - c\bar{t}) + \phi_0 \right] - \bar{m}\bar{x} - d \tag{1}$$

$$H_2 = a_2 \sin \left[\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (\bar{X} - c\bar{t}) \right] + \bar{m}\bar{x} + d \tag{2}$$

Here the amplitudes of the waves, width of the channel and phase difference $a_1, a_2, 2d, \phi$ satisfy the condition for the divergent channel at the inlet of flow

$$a_1^2 + a_2^2 + 2a_1a_2 \cos(\phi) \leq 4d^2 \tag{3}$$

The transformation between moving frame (\bar{x}, \bar{y}) and fixed frame (\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) is given by

$$\bar{x} = \bar{X} - c\bar{t}, \bar{y} = \bar{Y}, \bar{u} = \bar{U} - c, \bar{v} = \bar{V}, p(x) = P(X, t) \tag{4}$$

The nondimensional quantities are given below:

$$\begin{aligned} h_1d = H_1, h_2d = H_2, x\lambda = \bar{x}, ad = a_1, bd = a_2, md = \lambda\bar{m}, \\ \psi cd = \bar{\psi}, uc = \bar{u}, t\lambda = c\bar{t}, \delta\lambda = d, Nt = \frac{\tau D_f (T_1 - T_0)}{T_m \nu}, \\ Nb = \frac{\tau D_b (C_1 - C_0)}{\nu}, p = \frac{d^2 \bar{p}}{\mu c \lambda}, M = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{\mu} B_0}, Re = \frac{\rho_f cd}{\mu}, \tag{5} \\ \theta = \frac{(T - T_0)}{(T_1 - T_0)}, \phi = \frac{(C - C_0)}{(C_1 - C_0)}, Gr_f = \frac{(1 - C_0) \rho_f g \alpha d^2 (T_1 - T_0)}{c \mu}, \\ Gr_c = \frac{(\rho_p - \rho_f) \rho_f g \beta d^2 (C_1 - C_0)}{c \mu}, Pr = \frac{\rho \mu c_f}{k_0}, Rn = \frac{16 \sigma^* T_0^3}{3 K \mu c_f} \end{aligned}$$

Kothandapani and Prakash [18] gave the following system of dimensionless partial differential equations that governs the fluid flow under the assumption of low Reynolds number and long wave length approximation

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^3 \psi}{\partial y^3} - M \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} + Gr_f \theta + Gr_c \phi + \frac{\sin \alpha}{T} \tag{6}$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} = 0 \tag{7}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2} + \frac{Pr Nb}{(1 + Pr Rn)} \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} \right) \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{Pr Nt}{(1 + Pr Rn)} \left(\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} \right)^2 = 0 \tag{8}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial^2 y^2} + \frac{Nt}{Nb} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial^2 y^2} = 0 \tag{9}$$

The corresponding boundary conditions are

$$\psi = \frac{Q}{2} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} + L \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} = -1, \theta = \phi = 1 \text{ at } y = h_2 = b \sin(2\pi x) + 1 + mx \tag{10}$$

$$\psi = -\frac{Q}{2} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} - L \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} = -1, \theta = \phi = 0 \text{ at } y = h_1 = -a \sin[2\pi x + \phi_0] - 1 - mx$$

IV. SOLUTION OF THE PROBLEM

Solving equations (6)- (9) subject to the boundary conditions (10), we obtain the velocity, temperature and nanoparticles concentration as

$$u = c_1 \cosh My + c_2 \sinh My + \frac{P}{M^2} + Gr_t \left[\frac{k_2}{M^2} - \frac{k_3 e^{-lk_1 y}}{(lk_1)^2 - M^2} \right] \tag{11} \theta = k_2 + k_3 e^{-lk_1 y} \tag{12}$$

$$+ Gr_c \left[\frac{Ntk_3 e^{-lk_1 y}}{Nb((lk_1)^2 - M^2)} + \frac{k_1}{M^2} y + \frac{k_4}{M^2} \right] + \frac{F'}{M^2}$$

$$\phi = -\frac{Nt}{Nb} k_3 e^{-lk_1 y} + k_1 y + k_4 \tag{13}$$

Integrating equation (11) and using the condition $\psi = 0$ at $y = 0$, we get the stream function as

$$\psi = \frac{c_1}{M} \sinh My + \frac{c_2}{M} \cosh My + \frac{P}{M^2} y + Gr_t \left[\frac{k_2}{M^2} y + \frac{k_3 e^{-lk_1 y}}{(lk_1)((lk_1)^2 - M^2)} \right] \tag{14}$$

$$- Gr_c \left[\frac{Ntk_3 e^{-lk_1 y}}{Nb((lk_1)((lk_1)^2 - M^2)} + \frac{k_1}{2M^2} y^2 + \frac{k_4}{M^2} y \right] + \frac{F'}{M^2} y$$

The volumetric flow rate Θ through each cross section in the wave frame is given by

$$\Theta = \int_{h_1}^{h_2} u dy = P \left[g_1(y) \right]_{y=h_1}^{y=h_2} + \left[g_2(y) \right]_{y=h_1}^{y=h_2} \tag{15}$$

where $g_1(y) = \left[\frac{-1}{M^2 t_1} \sinh My + \left(\frac{t_1 - t_4}{M^2 (t_2 t_4 - t_3 t_1)} \right) \left(\frac{\cosh My}{M} - \frac{t_2 \sinh My}{t_1 M} \right) + \frac{y}{M^2} \right] \tag{16}$

$$g_2(y) = -\frac{(1+t_3) \sinh My}{Mt_1} + \left[\frac{t_1 - t_4 - t_3 t_4 + t_2 t_1}{t_2 t_4 - t_3 t_1} \right] \left[\frac{\cosh My}{M} - \frac{t_2 \sinh My}{t_1 M} \right] + Gr_t \frac{k_2}{M^2} y + \frac{k_3 Gr_t}{(lk_1)((lk_1)^2 - M^2)} e^{-lk_1 y} - \frac{k_3 Gr_c Nt}{(Nb)(lk_1)((lk_1)^2 - M^2)} e^{-lk_1 y} + Gr_c \frac{k_4}{M^2} y + \frac{F'}{M^2} y + Gr_c \frac{k_1}{2M^2} y^2$$

The instantaneous volumetric flow rate Q in the laboratory frame of reference is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q &= \int_{H_1}^{H_2} U dY \\
 &= \Theta + h_2 - h_1
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

From equation (15), the pressure gradient is given as

$$\frac{dp}{dx} = - \left[\frac{\Theta - g_2(h_2) + g_2(h_1)}{g_1(h_2) - g_1(h_1)} \right] \tag{18}$$

The time-averaged flow rate F is given by

$$F = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T Q dt = \Theta + 2(mx + 1) \tag{19}$$

Integrating (18) with respect to x over one wavelength, we get the pressure rise(drop) over one cycle of wave as

$$\Delta p = - \int_0^1 \left[\frac{\Theta - g_2(h_2) + g_1(h_1)}{g_1(h_2) - g_1(h_1)} \right] dx \tag{20}$$

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To analyze the variations on pressure rise, velocity, temperature and concentration profiles with respect to various

physical parameters we used the following fixed values: $M = 1, Nb = 3, Nt = 2, \alpha = \frac{\pi}{3}, \phi_0 = \frac{\pi}{4}, Rn = 1, Pr = 1, Gr_t = 0.5,$

$$Gr_c = 1.5, L = 1, a = 0.12, b = 0.2, x = 0.6, m = 0.2$$

Pressure rise profiles

The variation of pressure rise with time averaged flow rate is calculated from equation (20) for different physical parameters such as Hartmann number M , inclination parameter α , Brownian motion parameter Nt , Thermophoresis parameter Nb , non-uniform parameter m , slip parameter L , mass Grashof number Gr_c , temperature Grashof number Gr_t and the results are shown in the Figures (1)-(8). From Figure (1), it is observed that the pressure rise increases with increasing Hartmann number in the pumping region $0 < F < 2$ and the opposite behavior is noticed in the region $F > 2$. From Figures (2),(4)-(8), it is evident that the pressure rise increases with increasing inclination, thermophoresis, non-uniform, slip parameters, temperature and mass Grashof numbers and the converse behavior is observed in the case of increasing Brownian motion parameter. The results are similar to the results of Saima Noreen et al.[14].

Velocity profiles

The variation of Gr_c , Gr_t , M , L , m , Nt , Nb on velocity is calculated from the expression (12) and the results are shown in Figures (9)-(14). Figures (9) and (10) shows that the velocity decreases in left of the channel and increases in the right of the channel with increasing temperature, mass Grashof numbers and it is also noticed that the velocity profiles are more slanted towards the right of the channel due to the slip effect. Due to the effect of Hartmann number and slip parameter, the velocity increases near the walls of the channel and decreases at the centre of the channel and it is evident from the Figures (11)-(12). Figure (13) shows that the velocity decreases with

increasing non-uniformity of the channel. Figure (14) reveals that the velocity decreases with Brownian motion parameter in the left of the channel and opposite behavior is observed in the right of the channel. The effect of thermophoresis parameter on the velocity profiles is shown in Figure(15) and it is noticed that the velocity decreases at the walls of the channel and increases at the centre of the channel. The same trend is observed by Kothendapani and Prakesh[18]

Temperature profiles

The variation in temperature profiles for different m , Nt , Nb , Pr , Rn is calculated from the equation (11) and the results are shown in Figures (16)-(20). From Figure (16), as the non-uniform parameter increases, the temperature increases from the left of channel to the centre of the channel and then reverse trend is observed in right half of the channel. The increasing values of, Brownian motion, thermophoresis parameters and Prandtl number enhances

the temperature whereas the converse trend is observed in the case of radiation parameter. The same behavior is observed by Sreenadh et al. [20]

Concentration profiles

The effects of m , Nt , Nb , Pr , Rn on nanoparticle concentration are calculated from the equation (12) and the results are shown in Figures (21)-(25). The effect of non-uniform parameter on concentration profiles is shown in the Figure (26) and it is revealed that the nanoparticle concentration increases with increasing non-uniform parameter. From Figures (27)-(28), Brownian motion parameter and thermophoresis parameter have opposite behavior on the concentration profiles. Nanoparticle concentration decreases with the increasing values of Prandtl number whereas increases with the radiation parameter. The trends are similar to the results of Sreenadh [20].

Figure 1. Variation of pressure rise for different M

Figure 2. Variation of pressure rise for different inclination parameter

Figure 3. Variation of pressure rise for different Nt

Figure 4. Variation of pressure rise for different Nb

Figure 5. Variation of pressure rise for different m

Figure 6. Variation of pressure rise for different L

Figure 7. Variation of pressure rise for different Gr_t

Figure 8. Variation of pressure rise for different Gr_c

Figure 9. Variation of velocity u for different Gr_t

Figure 10. Variation of velocity u for different Gr_c

Figure 11. Variation of velocity u for different M

Figure 12. Variation of velocity u for different L

Figure 13. Variation of velocity u for different m

Figure 14. Variation of velocity u for different Nt

Figure 15. Variation of velocity u for different Nb

Figure 16. Variation of velocity u for different m

Figure 17. Variation of temperature θ for different Nt

Figure 18. Variation of temperature θ for different Nb

Figure 19. Variation of temperature θ for different Pr

Figure 20. Variation of temperature θ for different Rn

Figure 21. Variation of nanoparticle concentration ϕ for different m

Figure 22. Variation of nanoparticle concentration ϕ for different Nt

Figure 23. Variation of nanoparticle concentration ϕ for different Nb

Figure 24. Variation of nanoparticle concentration ϕ for different Pr

Figure 24. Variation of nanoparticle concentration ϕ for different Rn

VI. STREAMLINES

The streamlines are drawn for different M, Nb, Nt, α by using the expression (14) and the results are presented in Figures (30)-(31). It is observed that as the magnetic effect increases the number of trapped bolos decreases at the right wall of the channel.

Figure 25. (a) $M=1$

(b) $M=1.5$

(c) $M=2$

Figure26. (d) $Nb=3.5$

(e) $Nb=4$

(f) $Nb=4.5$

Figure 27. (g) $Nt=3.5$

(h) $Nt=4$

(i) $Nt=4$

Figure 28. (k) $\alpha = \pi/4$ (l) $\alpha = \pi/3$ (m) $\alpha = \pi/2$

VII. Conclusions

The peristaltic transport of a conducting Newtonian nanofluid in an tapered asymmetric inclined channel with the effects of velocity slip, heat and mass transfer in wave frame is investigated. The main findings of the present work are listed below:

1. The pumping rate increases with increasing inclination parameter in all regions.
2. The velocity profiles increases at the walls of the channel and decreases at the centre of the channel with increasing magnetic parameter and slip parameter.
3. In the case of temperature distribution, the Brownian motion and thermophoresis parameters shows same effect but these two parameters shows opposite behaviour on nanoparticles concentration.
4. The size of the trapped bolos increases with the increasing magnetic effect.

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